

REQUIREMENTS OF THE MODERN TEACHER

Ilmurodova Feruza Shokirovna

Teacher of history at school No. 275 of Mirzo Ulugbek district of Tashkent

Annotation. The article describes the graduates of higher education and teachers of general secondary education and the tasks set for them, the formation of new competencies, readiness to solve various problems in non-standard situations, as well as the active participation of high-class teachers. There are comments on the methods of preparation and their preparation.

Keywords: communicative, organization of the educational process, source of knowledge, competence, model, purposefulness, creative personality, modern teacher, attractiveness, competition.

Аннотация: Мақоллада oily ta`lim bitiruvchilari hamda umumiy o`rta ta'lim muassasalarining o'qituvchilari va ularning oldiga qo'yilgan vazifalar, yangi kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish, nostandart vaziyatlarda turli muammolarni hal qilishga tayyor bo'lishi, shuningdek, yuqori toifali o'qituvchilarning faol o'qitish usullari va ularning tayyorgarligi haqida fikr-mulohazalar keltirib o`tilgan.

Калит сўзлар: kommunikativ, ta'lim jarayonini tashkil etish, bilim manbai, kompetentsiya, namuna, maqsadlilik, ijodiy shaxs, zamonaviy o'qituvchi, jozibadorlik, raqobat, o'qituvchi, o'quvchi, o'rganish, fazilatlar, bola, tarbiya.

Аннотация. В статье описаны выпускники высшей вузы и преподаватели общего среднего образования и поставленные перед ними задачи, формирование новых компетенций, готовность решать различные задачи в нестандартных ситуациях, а также активное участие преподавателей высокого класса. Имеются комментарии к способам приготовления и их приготовлению.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативный, организация, источник знаний, модель, творческая личность, современный педагог, компетентность, конкуренция.

Education is an integral part of any society, it is constantly modernizing, because without changing the education system, society can not develop dynamically. Educated and literate people are the main driving force of human development in the 21st century. In the modern world, education is the most important condition for the growth of social and economic well-being, a resource for the sustainable development of the country. As the President said, “Education is a matter of the future, life and death. Therefore, we have no right to delay reforms in this area. No matter how difficult it is, we must lay a solid foundation for school education today. Because we have lost a lot of time. ”[1] That is why the reform of education, modernization in line with international requirements, is a key priority today. However, there are still problems in education that need to be addressed, and the process of training teachers with high professional and pedagogical competence remains relevant. According to statistics, today out of more than 504,000 teachers in the country, 12% have secondary special education, and 38% have no qualifications at all. Problems such as insufficient teaching skills of teachers, lack of effective system of self-motivation and motivation of teachers in educational institutions, in most cases, the teacher's desire for teaching hours, rather than quality teaching [2] It is necessary to pay special attention to.

Education is a system that determines an individual's ability to act properly in any day-to-day situation [3], and in the context of globalization, the rapidly changing world requires education to be reformed accordingly. Education is also a new idea in response to globalization. It is necessary to introduce approaches and technologies into the system, to develop the volume of theoretical knowledge, the dynamics of practical activities and the direction of independent work of students. K. D. Ushinsky emphasizes that the teacher "at the level of modern education should feel like a living, active member of a great organism that fights against the evils of ignorance and humanity, as a mediator between all that is noble and noble in the past." He feels like a living fighter between the past and the future, a mighty fighter

for truth and goodness, and realizes that his work, his seemingly humble deeds, is one of the greatest deeds in history, and that kingdoms are based on it and that all generations live on.

Gradually, the traditional, knowledge-only school of the past has become a thing of the past, and a new historical type of development school, schools aimed at preparing students for life, logical thinking and highly competent students, is becoming more active. At the same time, education is, of course, a consumer of creative staff, interested in the development and implementation of new curricula, aspiring to research, able to use innovative pedagogical technologies, which is a constant in the teaching profession. means high demand. Education is a type of activity that is discussed in detail and evaluated by subjects and individually. . Therefore, the professional and pedagogical competence of a modern teacher is always a central issue. The teacher-student relationship has also been a hotly debated topic for centuries.

Analyzing the methodological literature, it can be said that a teacher who is a leading expert in the field of education is a person who uses lessons and instructions based on effective experience in any field of knowledge. He performs the main task of his profession to the best of his ability, conveying the information he has acquired during his career, helping the student to develop the ability to know and develop the world [4].

It also teaches how to understand, process and use information independently. This can be achieved by teachers with the following characteristics:

- loves children and is able to show interest in them;
- knows the psychology of schoolchildren of different ages;
- appreciates the uniqueness of the child's personality;

- observation of children's behavior and drawing conclusions;
- can assess the intellectual potential and build a strategy for the individual development of the child;
- easily communicates with children, earns their love and respect;
- successfully manages the children's team;
- knows his subject in depth;
- prepared for innovation and striving for development, etc.

The teaching profession must also have a high level of moral qualities. The teacher should get acquainted with the social passport of students, which allows the teacher to organize work with students in a systematic and targeted manner. However, it should be noted that the teacher is prohibited from disclosing confidential information about children and their families. If a teacher analyzes his / her work and thinks about how to develop it, he / she will achieve a lot. There are 8 most important features of modern students, which are listed below:

- easy comprehension of information;
- high intellectual potential and its various manifestations;
- ability to quickly master technical devices, electronic innovations;
- poor focus on real world problems;
- low level of intellectual activity;
- low level of social and communicative competence;
- insufficient self-control;
- decreased motivation to learn, etc.

Such diverse characteristics of modern children create special conditions for the creativity of the teacher. By learning new approaches and preserving the pedagogical discoveries of previous years, a true professional who is dedicated to his work can create his own education system. The teacher should have an interesting, mysterious and situational level of mobility for each child. Thus, at the current stage of development of society, it can be concluded that a modern learner needs an innovative teacher. A teacher is not only an expert in his or her subject, not only a psychologist, a researcher, but also a bright, creative person capable of self-improvement, love, and happiness. Today's teacher must have his own word, his own position and status, to educate young people as a shield against any stones thrown at the country. Thus, the interest in this profession will increase and a system of competitive training will be developed.

References:

1. Video conference meeting chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on January 28, 2022.
2. From the report of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "We have lost a lot of time", Gazeta .uz January 28, 2022.
3. Sayidova S. Yo. Problems of perspective development of education: materials VIII Mejdunar. nauch. konf. (Krasnodar, February 2016) Krasnodar 2016. pp. 14-17.
4. Shumskaya O. A. Pridvoreva O. G. Education: proshloe, nastoyashchee i budushchee: materials V Mejdunar. nauch. konf. (g. Krasnodar, November 2018) - Krasnodar 2018. pp. 43-45.